

PEDAGOGICAL POSSIBILITIES OF TUTORING IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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Annotation: This thesis analyzes the pedagogical possibilities of introducing and developing the tutoring system in higher education institutions. The role and importance of tutoring activities in supporting the personal and professional development of students, forming their independent learning skills, increasing their motivation, and effectively organizing the processes of social adaptation are scientifically highlighted. Also, the pedagogical conditions of tutoring activities, its functions based on modern requirements, and the requirements for the professional competence of tutors are analyzed.

Keywords: tutoring, higher education, pedagogical opportunities, student personality, independent learning, individual approach, professional development, motivation, quality of education.

Introduction.

The priority of innovative and person-oriented approaches in the 21st century education system requires a fundamental rethinking of the content and forms of education in higher education institutions. The need to form students as individuals who are adaptable to the modern professional and social environment, independent thinkers, creative and critical thinkers requires the improvement of pedagogical technologies and the introduction of new professional roles into the educational process - in particular, the position of a tutor.

Tutoring is a specific type of activity aimed at forming an individual educational path (trajectory) of a student and providing him with practical and pedagogical assistance, which aims to strengthen educational motivation, manage independent educational activities and form a personal development strategy. Tutoring is closely related to the basic principles of modern pedagogy - an individual approach, reflective analysis, self-development and competency-based approaches.

The introduction of tutoring in the higher education system, on the one hand, serves to take into account the individual needs, interests and educational opportunities of students, and on the other hand, increases the effectiveness of the educational process, expands the possibilities for monitoring the quality of education and diagnosing personal achievements. A tutor is not only an academic assistant, but also a person who manages the personal and

professional growth of a student, actively participates in the processes of his self-awareness, self-development and social adaptation. The relevance of the thesis is that in today's conditions of globalization and digital transformation, higher education institutions are faced with the task of organizing personalized, flexible and result-oriented education. From this point of view, it is scientifically and practically important to analyze the pedagogical possibilities of tutoring activities, determine their role and significance in the higher education process. This thesis analyzes in detail the essence of the tutoring system, pedagogical conditions, types of activity and mechanisms of influence, and sheds light on the role of tutoring in the personal and professional development of students in higher education on a scientific basis.

In the higher education system, tutoring is an important methodological tool in the formation of a student's individual development strategy, the development of independent learning skills and the organization of a personalized learning process. The pedagogical essence of tutoring is determined, first of all, by the creation of a reflexive educational environment that allows the student to understand his own educational activities, personal abilities and professional aspirations.

In pedagogical literature, tutoring is characterized by a number of main functions:

educational-facilitative function - supporting the student's independent decision-making and freedom of choice in the process of learning;

motivational-facilitative function - the formation and maintenance of internal motivation for educational activities;

diagnostic function - determining the individual educational needs, abilities and level of development of the student;

consultative-facilitative function - designing individual educational trajectories and providing advice on them;

monitoring and reflection function - active participation of the student in assessing the educational process and results.

From a pedagogical point of view, tutoring activities are carried out on the basis of the principles of a person-centered approach, subject-subject communication and support for independent learning. In this case, the tutor conducts pedagogical activities aimed at forming an individual educational project with the student, strengthening his knowledge, skills and competencies.

Today, tutors in higher education institutions act not only as assistants providing an individualized form of educational programs, but also as

pedagogical facilitators, mentors, educational consultants and specialists providing psychological support. This, in turn, requires a high level of professional and methodological requirements for tutoring activities. Thus, the institute of tutoring in the higher education system is considered as a pedagogical mechanism that serves to humanize the educational process, develop personally oriented learning strategies, and form the competence of self-awareness and development of learners.

Literature analysis:

Theoretical and practical research on the formation and development of tutoring activities in the higher education system is being widely analyzed in modern pedagogy. In particular, I. S. Yakimanskaya, in her research, identified the main role of the tutor in the formation of individual educational trajectories and developed a tutoring methodology based on the principles of personally oriented education. The author justifies the need to expand the student's ability to manage his own cognitive activity on the basis of independent choice.

As researchers such as V. A. Bolotov and E. S. Polat have noted, tutoring is considered not only a means of increasing academic achievement, but also an important pedagogical mechanism for the formation of a student's self-awareness and development competence. In their opinion, tutoring activity requires the creation of a reflexive learning environment that serves the development of the student's personality.

Modern studies, in particular, the works of D. V. Grigoriev and M. M. Potashnik, analyze the implementation of modern forms and technologies of tutoring activity in higher education through the methods of educational support (coaching), mentoring and facilitation. They emphasize that the success of tutoring activity depends, first of all, on the establishment of a trusting and reflexive dialogue between the student and the tutor.

Foreign researchers, including R. Race and S. Topping, have deeply studied the psychological and socio-pedagogical aspects of tutoring activity in education. They present tutoring as an effective mechanism for developing mutual assistance, academic support, and social adaptation among students.

Also, local scientists, in particular, the "Concept for the Development of Tutoring Activities in the Higher Education System" developed by the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Specialized Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan, specifically emphasizes the need to develop a national model of tutoring in higher education, form its regulatory and legal framework, and develop a system

of professional training. Based on the analyzed literature, the following main theoretical and practical aspects of tutoring in higher education are identified:

identifying the student's personal educational needs and forming individual development paths;

developing a methodology for effective organization and management of independent educational activities;

basing the educational process on the principles of personalization and humanization;

expanding opportunities for reflection, self-awareness, and the development of social competencies.

At the same time, the analysis of the literature shows the need to further develop scientific and methodological foundations for the effective organization of tutoring activities in higher education, improve the professional competence of tutors, and improve mechanisms for monitoring their activities.

Discussion:

Tutoring activities play an important role as an innovative pedagogical mechanism in the formation of individual development strategies of students in higher education institutions, the development of self-management and reflexive competencies. During the discussion, it was found that tutoring, on the one hand, activates the processes of self-awareness, independent learning, professional identification and self-development of the student, and on the other hand, serves to implement a person-oriented approach in the educational and educational activities of the educational institution.

From a pedagogical point of view, the main determinant ensuring the effectiveness of tutoring activities is the process of forming the student's personal educational trajectory and consciously managing it. This process includes the following main pedagogical components:

strengthening the student's internal motivation based on a motivational-competence approach;

assessment and development of the student's own knowledge and skills through reflexive analysis;

development and implementation of individualized learning strategies;

strengthening social interaction between students through the active use of cooperative learning methods (coaching, mentoring, facilitation).

Research shows that the successful implementation of tutoring in the higher education system depends on a number of necessary pedagogical conditions and criteria. In particular:

high professional and methodological training of tutors;
the availability of mechanisms for developing individual development programs and monitoring them;
the openness of the educational environment and the formation of a system of socio-psychological support.

Tutoring activities allow students to develop competencies such as self-development, critical thinking, and career planning. These competencies, in turn, play an important role in the process of training competitive and socially active specialists, which is the main goal of a higher education institution and meets the needs of society.

During the discussion, it is also worth noting that tutoring activities in the higher education system require not only rebuilding the relationship between the teacher and the student, but also updating the entire educational and educational activities of the educational institution based on the concept of person-centered education. In this case, pedagogical facilitation, personal development monitoring, self-awareness and reflection technologies are considered as central methodological elements of tutoring activities. Based on the analyzed theoretical and practical sources, it can be said that for the effective functioning of the tutoring institute in higher education, an integrated approach is required: it is necessary to improve pedagogical technologies, systematize the professional development of tutors, as well as introduce innovative management and monitoring mechanisms in educational institutions.

Conclusion.

Based on the analysis, it can be concluded that the development of tutoring activities in higher educational institutions is an effective pedagogical tool for increasing the personal orientation of the educational process, forming students' independent learning competencies, and increasing their level of professional and social adaptation. Tutoring activities, first of all, expand the opportunities for designing educational trajectories in accordance with the individual needs, aspirations, and abilities of students, strengthening their educational motivation, and forming self-development and reflexive activity skills.

The widespread introduction of the tutoring institute in the higher education system creates the basis for training highly qualified and competitive personnel by improving the quality of education, stimulating student activity, and developing a culture of self-management. From this point of view, the development of the tutoring system in higher education institutions on a

scientific and methodological basis and its widespread implementation in practice is considered an urgent and promising pedagogical task.

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